

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

6th TESSE2b Workshop & B2B Meeting | Austria

The 6th TESSE2b Workshop/B2B took place in Graz, Austria (10 April) and it was another opportunity for TESSE2b partners to discuss and share information with external entities. TESSE2b partners presented their works and other H2020 R&D projects (CREATE and SCORES) have also disseminated their activities. The event also included a visit to the Austrian demosite, which allowed to verify the installation works.

Don't miss next
TESSE2b

Workshops/B2B Meetings:
Poland | 12 June
Portugal | 18 September

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](#)

AUSTRIA DEMOSITE

The ambient heating is officially in operation at Austria demosite by thermal solar collectors with the support of GSHP and 3 PCM tanks. At the same time, thermal solar collectors produce DHW which energy is stored in a PCM tank.

Stay tuned to next Newsletters for more updates!

